

**METHODS OF IMPROVING ENGLISH SPEAKING COMPETENCE THROUGH
TECHNICAL TERMINOLOGY OF ESP LEARNERS IN HIGHER EDUCATION***Shaxnoza Xakinjanovna Yusupaliyeva**Lecturer, Oriental University, Uzbekistan*

Abstract: This article devotes to improve ESP learners' speaking competence through technical vocabulary and development requires effective strategies that integrate both acquisition and practical application. Contextual learning, which emphasizes teaching vocabulary in meaningful and realistic situations, enhances retention and usage. One of the most effective approaches is using authentic materials such as newspapers, podcasts, videos, and dialogues to introduce technical vocabulary in context.

Key words: speaking competence, ESP, authentic materials, vocabulary acquisition, real-life context, audiovisual resources, vocabulary retention.

Introduction: In today's globalized world, proficiency in English, particularly in specialized fields, is essential for effective communication. English for Specific Purposes (ESP) focuses on equipping learners with the necessary language skills tailored to their professional or academic domains. One critical aspect of ESP is mastering technical terminology, which plays a vital role in enhancing learners' speaking competence. Without a strong grasp of field-specific vocabulary, learners may struggle to communicate effectively in professional settings. Contextual learning has emerged as an effective approach to improving learners' speaking competence by integrating technical vocabulary in meaningful and realistic situations. By using authentic materials such as industry-specific texts, podcasts, videos, and real-world dialogues, learners can develop a deeper understanding of technical terms and their practical applications. Additionally, interactive strategies such as role-playing, case studies, and simulations help reinforce vocabulary retention and promote active usage in communication.

It various methods for improving ESP learners' English-speaking competence through technical terminology. It highlights the significance of contextual learning, authentic materials, and interactive teaching techniques in fostering vocabulary acquisition and practical application. By implementing these strategies, educators can enhance learners' ability to communicate effectively in professional and academic environments.

In contrast to conventional approaches, which emphasize grammatical correctness above everything else, communicative competence covers a wider range of language use. It includes the capacity to use language effectively and appropriately in a variety of social circumstances in addition to the proper use of syntax and vocabulary. In today's globalized world, where proficient English communication can greatly improve possibilities for academic, professional, and personal growth, this all-encompassing approach to language learning is essential.

Fundamentally, communicative competence combines a number of important elements. Among these are linguistic competence, which deals with vocabulary, syntax, and morphology; sociolinguistic competence, which entails knowing how

Main part: Improving learners' speaking competence through technical vocabulary involves a combination of strategies that target both the acquisition of vocabulary and its practical application in communication in the field of industry. Below are some effective methods of contextual learning. While using authentic materials introduce vocabulary in context through real-life materials like newspapers, podcasts, videos, or dialogues. It encourages learners to use new vocabulary in storytelling, enhancing retention and context understanding. A part from it, engage learners in simulations of real-life situations where specific vocabulary is required. Contextual learning focuses on teaching vocabulary in meaningful and realistic situations rather than in isolation. By providing a natural and relevant context, learners better understand how words are used and are more likely to retain and apply them effectively. Below are some ways to implement contextual learning for vocabulary development with the help of real-life materials:

- **Authentic texts:** Use materials like newspapers, magazines, novels, menus, or brochures to expose learners to vocabulary in its natural context.
- **Audio-visual resources:** Include podcasts, TV shows, movies, and YouTube videos to demonstrate how vocabulary is used in everyday speech. The use of real-world materials, such as industry-specific texts, podcasts, and videos, exposes learners to natural language use in professional settings. Authentic materials not only enhance vocabulary acquisition but also improve listening and comprehension skills. However, the complexity of some materials may pose challenges for lower-proficiency learners, necessitating scaffolding techniques such as guided reading and vocabulary pre-teaching. The effectiveness of improving ESP learners' English-speaking competence through technical terminology depends on the integration of contextual learning, authentic materials, and interactive teaching methods. This section analyzes the impact of these strategies on learners' vocabulary acquisition, retention, and practical application in professional communication.

Another method of task-based learning to design tasks that require learners to use specific vocabulary to achieve a goal. Tasks could include planning an event, creating a budget, or solving a problem. Role-playing, simulations, and collaborative discussions encourage active vocabulary use and improve speaking fluency. Research indicates that learners who practice technical terminology through interactive methods develop greater confidence and accuracy in their speech. Moreover, problem-solving tasks and case studies promote critical thinking while reinforcing subject-specific vocabulary in meaningful ways. Despite the advantages of contextual learning, certain challenges exist. Learners with limited exposure to technical English may struggle with comprehension, requiring additional support through glossaries, visual aids, and structured practice activities. Additionally, educators must ensure that speaking tasks align with learners' professional goals to maximize engagement and relevance. The analysis highlights the effectiveness of contextual learning strategies in enhancing ESP learners' speaking competence through technical terminology. While authentic materials and interactive methods promote vocabulary retention and application, educators must address potential challenges by providing structured guidance and support.

A part from this, interactive activities like to use games like role-plays, simulations, or problem-solving activities where learners actively use the vocabulary. Improved application learners can immediately apply vocabulary in relevant situations. Greater understanding context

clarifies nuances, connotations, and appropriate usage. Engagement in real-life contexts make learning more interesting and relatable.

By immersing learners in meaningful contexts, vocabulary learning becomes more natural, practical, and effective, fostering their overall communicative competence. Thematic Vocabulary Building topic-based learning in-group vocabulary around themes (e.g., travel, health, or technology) to create meaningful connections. Word webs and mind maps: Encourage learners visually organize related words around a central topic.

In conclusion, the analysis highlights the effectiveness of contextual learning strategies in enhancing ESP learners' speaking competence through technical terminology. While authentic materials and interactive methods promote vocabulary retention and application, educators must address potential challenges by providing structured guidance and support. In teaching vocabulary in context introduce words through real-life scenarios or activities that reflect the theme. Use dialogues, articles, or videos to demonstrate usage. In using visual and graphic organizers word webs improves place the central theme in the middle and connect related words around it. In conclusion, the analysis highlights the effectiveness of contextual learning strategies in enhancing ESP learners' speaking competence through technical terminology. While authentic materials and interactive methods promote vocabulary retention and application, educators must address potential challenges by providing structured guidance and support.

To sum up, to effectively teach vocabulary in context, integrate real-life scenarios and activities that align with specific themes. Charts and tables further organize vocabulary with columns for synonyms, antonyms, and example sentences. Enhancing ESP learners' English-speaking competence through technical terminology requires a combination of contextual learning, authentic materials, and interactive teaching strategies. Contextualized vocabulary instruction allows learners to understand and retain technical terms more effectively by associating them with real-world situations. Authentic materials, such as industry-specific texts, podcasts, and videos, expose learners to professional language use, while interactive techniques like role-playing, simulations, and case studies reinforce practical application. Despite some challenges, such as the complexity of technical materials and varying proficiency levels, these methods significantly improve learners' confidence and fluency in professional communication. By implementing structured support, including glossaries, visual aids, and guided practice, educators can help learners overcome difficulties and maximize their vocabulary acquisition.

In conclusion, integrating technical terminology through contextual learning not only enhances speaking competence but also prepares ESP learners for effective communication in their respective fields. A well-balanced approach that combines exposure, practice, and reinforcement is key to developing both linguistic accuracy and professional fluency.

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